

‘Farming with a jackal’: Power relations in Black-backed jackal (*Canidae: Lupulella mesomelas*) management around the Square Kilometre Array core site in South Africa

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ABSTRACT

A large body of work emphasises the importance of pluralist decision-making perspectives in wildlife management to incorporate multiple views of constituents. At the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) core site in South Africa, however, the scientific knowledge of astronomers and ecologists dominates local knowledge of farmers and farmworkers in Black-backed jackal (*Lupulella mesomelas*) management. Local farming communities adjacent to the site, recently proclaimed a national park, experience this scientific knowledge as oppressive and insufficient for their environment. This paper explores the relevance of local knowledge among commercial farmers and farmworkers in Black-backed jackal management, based largely on their experience of addressing livestock predation. We argue that incorporating local knowledge will promote wider acceptance of science-based Black-backed jackal management strategies, decrease farming community members’ sense of marginalisation from developments in their area and contribute to building trust among the social groups neighbouring the SKA core site, to the benefit of the astronomy project.

KEYWORDS: Black-backed jackal, conflict management, knowledge development, livestock farming, predation management, protected areas, South Africa, Square Kilometre Array

INTRODUCTION

Human–wildlife conflict encompasses negative interactions between humans and wildlife as well as conflictual interactions among humans, because of competing interests and/or value clashes in relation to animals; in other words, human–human conflict (Decker & Chase 1997; Madden 2004; Redpath *et al.* 2015; Terblanche 2015; Anand & Radhakrishna 2020). Both types of conflict may escalate “when local people feel that the needs or values of wildlife are given priority over their own needs, or when local institutions and people are inadequately empowered to deal with the conflict” (Madden 2004). The dynamics at play in and around the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) core site in the Northern Cape province, South Africa, are notably intricate and challenging. It has disrupted livestock farming and poses a continuing threat to the success of this major international radio astronomy project.

The SKA is an international effort to build the largest radio telescope in the world. With the other site located in Australia, South Africa hosts one of the two core facilities of this extraordinarily ambitious project, which is currently under construction on former farmland near Carnarvon in the Northern Cape province.

For small livestock farmers the arrival of the SKA as a major landowner in the Kareeberg constitutes a notable disruption of the social order in a region where they have long regarded themselves as *baas van die plaas* [master of the farm] (Terblanche 2020). This popular Afrikaans expression is generally used in the area, both by the farmers and other parties, and refers to someone who is clearly the boss. Although sheep farming has waned since the mid-twentieth century, commercial agriculture remains a principal economic and social driver in the region. As such, the state’s extensive land acquisition programme to secure the SKA core site posed a grave threat to the future of local farmers, whose remoteness from the decision-making centres of power compounded their sense of uncertainty and loss of agency in an already arduous economic climate. The decision to proclaim the core site as a national park has particularly aggrieved the sheep farmers neighbouring the area, as they anticipate it becoming a haven for Black-backed jackal (*Lupulella mesomelas*; hereafter jackal) and Caracal (*Caracal caracal*), the two main mesopredators implicated in livestock losses, especially of sheep, in South Africa.

The research on which this article draws addresses the overarching question: What are the dynamics shaping the farmer–jackal conflict on the farmlands

bordering the SKA core site in the Karoo region of South Africa’s Northern Cape province and what can we learn from this about jackal management and human–wildlife conflict? The following subsidiary research questions are explored in this paper:

- (1) What are the different understandings of jackals among the actors involved in jackal management in the SKA core site region, including ecologists, SKA SA managers and farmers?
- (2) What resources do the various jackal management actors draw on to justify their positions/understandings?
- (3) How are power relations around knowledge production rendered in jackal management?

In understanding the strain between farmers and the SKA in relation to jackal management, an appreciation of the very different knowledge systems that they mobilise in support of their views is significant. This paper contributes to the discussions surrounding the ‘scientific’ and ‘local’ bodies of knowledge in wildlife management. It provides insights into the divide between these knowledge types around jackal management and the tensions these dynamics have unleashed, which have compromised effective jackal management at the research site. We also show that there are some points of convergence in the knowledge systems that could facilitate ways forward.

With no broadly agreed-upon solution to the farmer–jackal conflict yet, nor institutional mechanisms to manage the differences between farmers and scientists, this paper is both topical and timely. Qualitative, sociological research such as this emphasises that the ecology of a region cannot be understood in isolation from the social relationships that are impacting upon and interacting with the environment. By highlighting the social dimensions of the farmer–jackal conflict in a context of significant and politically contested land-use change, this paper contributes to deepening the analysis of human–wildlife conflict (which has traditionally been considered a natural science area of concern) and underscores the importance of the social sciences in analysing the multifaceted dynamics of such conflicts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The core site of the SKA SA, which will host the “highest concentration of receivers” (197 dish antennas in total), lies approximately 90 km from Carnarvon in the Karoo region of the Northern Cape province of South Africa (SARAO 2023). Spanning approximately 427,000 km² across the western interior of the country, the arid and semi-arid Karoo is

renowned for its vastness, remoteness and seeming emptiness. Rainfall is very low, ranging from 100 mm per annum in the west to 500 mm per annum in the east (Esler *et al.* 2010; Hoffman 2015). The ecologically sensitive Karoo comprises two biomes: The Succulent Karoo in the west and south-west, and the Nama Karoo, which stretches eastwards across the interior plateau. Less than 1% of the Nama Karoo, in which the study site is located, is formally protected (Milton & Dean 2015). Because of the low rainfall and consequent low productivity, the Karoo is sparsely populated with less than a million people; *ca* 1.9% of South Africa’s population (Henschel *et al.* 2018), with its towns few and far between.

In 2008, the National Research Foundation (NRF) purchased the first two farms for this site in the Kareeberg area, in total approximately 14,000 ha. Initially, local people were under the impression that the two land parcels would be sufficient for the entire first phase of the SKA project and that livestock farming would be able to co-exist with the radio telescopes. However, in late 2015, farmers were disillusioned when the SKA announced that a further 32 farms (approximately 120,000 ha) had to be acquired to safeguard their instruments against radio frequency interferences caused by human activity, such as the use of cell phones, electric fences, and petrol-driven cars. The SKA infrastructure will also extend beyond this core site onto 71 farm portions along three ‘spiral arms’ totalling approximately 1700 ha. Here the radio dishes will be much less concentrated than in the core site, with seven dish-antennas to be erected per spiral arm (Gaea Enviro (Pty) Ltd 2018). In 2017, it was announced that the SKA SA would be amalgamated with other South African radio astronomy projects to form the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO), an NRF facility responsible for managing all radio astronomy telescopes and programmes in South Africa (SARAO 2023).

Additional measures to provide protection from radio frequency interferences included establishing a set of concentric ‘Astronomy Advantage Areas’ around the core site, with associated regulations to limit radio frequency interferences (President of the Republic of South Africa 2008). Steps to declare the SARAO area a national park were initiated in 2018, culminating in the declaration of the Meerkat National Park (Fig. 1) by South Africa’s Minister of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment in March 2020 (Creecy 2020). The Meerkat National Park derives its name from the MeerKAT radio telescope, the precursor of the SKA radio telescope. The formal establishment of the park emphasises its dedication to scientific research, in which astronomy takes precedence.

This study was conducted in the shadow of the SKA by focusing primarily on the 31 privately-owned

Figure 1: A cartographic representation of the SKA 'land core', which has been recently proclaimed as a national park. (Source: SANParks 2022)

properties neighbouring this site. At the start of the study in May 2016, these farms were owned by 16 white, Afrikaans-speaking, mostly middle-aged male farmers.

Data collection and analysis

A critical qualitative sociological study was conducted to explore the farmer–jackal conflict and the most effective way to manage this relationship in the context of the SKA project and the human–human conflict surrounding it locally. Thus, it has been possible to look beyond individual role players to the broader social, cultural and political context in which they find themselves, and to see how these influences affect their reality (Fig. 2). The main data collection methods were in-depth semi-structured interviews, participant observation and documentary analysis over a period of three years.

A total of 36 individuals were interviewed between May 2016 and July 2019. It is difficult to place research participants in single, pre-defined categories, as some individuals can be assigned to more than one interest group (hence, the total in Table 1 is greater than 36), which are summarised, along with the 'jackal narrative' (see Results and Discussion) of the participants, in Table 1.

Of the 36 individuals interviewed, just over half (19) identified themselves as farmers in their primary occupation. Of these 19 farmers, one borders Alkantpan, the ballistic test range of the Armaments Corporation of South Africa (ARMSCOR)¹; two farm on properties that were bought for the core site through SKA SA's Land Acquisition Programme; six farm in the Kareeberg region and 10 farm on properties bordering the SKA core site. Formal interviews with farmworkers involved in jackal management proved

¹ In his report to the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research on the estimation of SKA Phase 1's agricultural economic and local economic impact, Kirsten (2016) noted that the cessation of farming activities on Alkantpan after 1987 had seen farmers neighbouring this site incurring livestock losses. Situated just outside of the small Northern Cape town of Copperton, it was important to get views from in and around Alkantpan to compare the experiences of this similar site with those related to the SKA core site.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the various constituencies with an express interest in jackal management in and around the SKA core site. (Source: Adapted from Terblanche 2020)

difficult but was compensated for by drawing on informal interactions with three farmworkers on two tracking and hunting excursions.

The other 17 individuals in the sample were interviewed in their official or professional capacity. These respondents included five ecologists, one social scientist, three predation management experts and specialist predator hunters, four specialist predator hunters (one of whom was also employed by the National Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries or DAFF, which has since changed its name to Department of Land Reform and Rural Development or DALRRD), one employee at ARMSCOR's Alkantpan ballistic test range, one representative of the Red Meat Producer's Organisation (RPO), one representative of the National Wool Growers' Association (NWGA) and the Predation Management Forum (PMF, which since changed its name to Predation Management South Africa or PMSA in late 2019), and one SARAO representative. The latter submitted a written response to an interview schedule for the SARAO representatives, in lieu of being interviewed in person. This written response was complemented by numerous research encounters and exchanges with a range of the SARAO representatives during the fieldwork phase of this study.

An observer-as-participant role allowed for observing the interactions between farmers and the SARAO

staff and engaging with them informally about their experiences of the meetings and the opinions of those present at various public meetings, information sessions and workshops (15 in total). In addition, it allowed for attendance of one closed meeting. This role also involved accompanying farmers and/or their foremen and farmworkers, and specialist predator hunters on hunting excursions (15 in total). This allowed for both observing and participating in their jackal management practices, e.g., setting up traps, patrolling the farm, working with and examining sheep, and hunting. Here, it is worth noting the meticulousness with which *voetjagters* (colloquially translated as 'foot soldiers'), farmworkers who are involved in predator hunting, go about setting up foothold traps for jackal and caracal. These experiences were valuable in contextualising the stories and experiences conveyed through the semi-structured interviews.

An open-coding technique was used to identify broad, common themes from interview transcripts. Through the iterative process of coding and classifying, five overarching themes were identified: different knowledge systems and their understandings of the jackal; farmers' insecurity in relation to both the jackal and the SKA; the power relations around knowledge production in jackal management; farmers' sense of nostalgia; and the contribution of the management and/or persecution of jackals to collective action. The first three themes are of particular relevance to this

Table 1. Summary of interest groups and their representation in the study.

Interest group	Assigned 'jackal narrative'	Number
Small-livestock farmers	Predominantly 'farmer jackal narrative'	23
SARAO representative	'Environmental jackal narrative'	1
Ecologists (of whom 2 are South African Environmental Observation Network representatives)	'Environmental jackal narrative', but with an understanding of the 'farmer jackal narrative'	5
Social scientist	'Environmental jackal narrative'	1
Predation management experts	'Environmental jackal narrative', but with an understanding of the 'farmer jackal narrative'	3
Specialist predator hunters	'Farmer jackal narrative'	8
National Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries official	'Farmer jackal narrative'	1
RPO representative	'Farmer jackal narrative'	1
NWGA representative	'Farmer jackal narrative'	1
PMF representative	'Farmer jackal narrative' but with an understanding of the 'environmental jackal narrative'	1
Alkantpan employees (past and current)	'Farmer jackal narrative'	2

article. To illustrate the identified themes, excerpts from the interview transcripts are selected and quoted verbatim in the presentation of the results.

The bulk of the interviews were conducted and transcribed in Afrikaans. Data were only translated into English during data analysis, but for the purposes of this paper, English verbatim translations are used. Most research participants were assigned first-name pseudonyms (in single quotation marks) to preserve their anonymity. Those research participants who are public players in the jackal management debate, and gave permission, are identified by their real names.

In addition to the thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews and field notes, a wide range of documents on farmer–jackal conflict, jackal management, the SKA, and the history of farming and conservation in the Karoo were examined using discourse and content analysis. Fables and folktales in which jackals feature as protagonists and supporting characters were particularly valuable as representations of real and imaginary relationships between humans (predominantly farmers) and jackals.

Specific attention was given to the 'interdiscursivity' of the texts (and images, where applicable), i.e. "identifying the presence and forms of combination of recurrent and relatively stable and durable 'discourses' in texts, and exploring their implications" (Sumares & Fidélis 2011). An open-coding technique was used to broadly distinguish between negative and positive

social constructions and/or discourses of jackals. Particular note was made of the anthropomorphic use of language in describing jackals as, for example, '*skelm*', '*slim*', 'thieves', 'adaptable' and 'crafty'. Similarly, the negatives and positives people perceived the SKA to bring to the Karoo communities were broadly distinguished and noted, particularly from whom the arguments and/or concerns came.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper explores the power dynamics around knowledge production in jackal management in and around the SKA core site and the marginalisation of local knowledge as a result. The SKA development appears to not only prioritise the pursuit of astronomy above local agricultural livelihoods in the Kareeberg area, but also build an alliance between the physical (i.e. astronomy) and the life sciences (i.e. ecology and zoology) in relation to the management of the SKA core site. Natural scientists (including both physical and life scientists) have been put at the helm of devising jackal management plans for the SKA core site and new national park, because of the assumed superiority of their scientific knowledge.

According to Taylor and de Løe (2012), the bias against local knowledge "highlights the critical relationship between knowledge and power in collaborative processes". Despite farmers being directly affected by this development, their concerns, inclu-

ding livestock predation, are disregarded, even belittled, along with their knowledge of the area and jackal management (Terblanche 2020). Nevertheless, a great deal of practical knowledge is found at the farm level, while some ‘lay experts’ straddle both local and scientific knowledge.

Different knowledge systems and understandings of the jackal

Wildlife management often relies on accepted scientific practices and is biased against local knowledge (Taylor & de Loe 2012). The attraction of scientific knowledge lies mostly in its (assumed) objectivity, verifiability, professionalism and expertise (Sundberg 1998; Pedykowski 2003; Taylor & de Loe 2012). Scientific knowledge accepts that knowledge-producing actions are only possible and make sense with the recognition of the existence of an “independent material reality” (Carolan 2005). In other words, scientific knowledge relies largely on natural science disciplines which view nature as an external given that can be more and more fully known through systematic observation, measurement, and experimentation. Furthermore, those who possess this type of knowledge are seen to “possess the truth about the natural world and how humans should interact with it” (Sundberg 1998).

In contrast to this elite approach which considers itself to be “the best and the only consistent way of producing reliable knowledge of the world” (Kloppenburger 1991), ‘local’ knowledge is defined as a “culturally generated and transmitted body of information that is context-dependent, experiential and garnered over generations” (Lute & Gore 2014; see also Corburn 2003). Agrawal (1995) adds that ‘local’ knowledge is “integrally linked with the lives of people, always produced in dynamic interactions among humans and between humans and nature” while also continuously changing.²

In his article on local knowledge for an alternative agriculture and the resultant need for a de/reconstruction of agricultural science, Kloppenburger (1991) identifies farmers and their workers as the epitome of local knowledge producers, reproducers and carriers. As elsewhere, the farming practices that have evolved in the Kareeberg region, including the local jackal management strategies, have been influenced and delimited by the Karoo’s unique social and physical environment.

In their sociological research on jackal ecology and management in the Central Karoo District Municipality of the Western Cape province, South Africa, Natrass and Conradie (2015) identified two rival ‘jackal narratives’ in which the tensions between ‘scientific’ and ‘local’ knowledge systems were clearly present: the ‘environmental jackal narrative’, rooted in ‘scientific’ knowledge, biocentrism and an objective, rationalist approach to jackal management, and the ‘farmer jackal narrative’, rooted in ‘local’ knowledge, anthropocentrism and an affective approach to jackal management.

The ‘environmental jackal narrative’ is predominantly associated with environmental groupings, which include ecologists and animal rights activists, and is “supported by the science of predator ecology” (Natrass & Conradie 2015). It is thus an expression of the ‘scientific’ knowledge system described above, which focuses on jackal populations and their role in broader ecological systems. The ecological sciences which underpin this narrative have highlighted the cruelty associated with the use of some predation management practices and argued that indiscriminate control may be counter-productive by disrupting the social structure of jackal populations (Minnie *et al.* 2016; see also Natrass & Conradie 2015; Natrass & Conradie 2018; Natrass *et al.* 2020a, 2020b), which may result in increased reproductive output in the face of high mortality and facilitate jackal movement across properties to fill vacant territories (Natrass & Conradie 2015; Minnie *et al.* 2016; Kamler *et al.* 2020; Natrass *et al.* 2020a). Those subscribing to the ‘environmental jackal narrative’ argue that to manage jackals effectively, farmers should rather make use of non-lethal control methods to protect their livestock and also “learn to live with the jackal” which means tolerating a certain amount of livestock losses; the costs of which can be offset by cheaper and ecologically more valuable benefits of co-existence (Natrass & Conradie 2015).

In contrast, the ‘farmer jackal narrative’ supports and justifies the lethal control of jackals. Most farmers and specialist predator hunters are of the opinion that, in the absence of lethal control, jackals will proliferate and livestock losses due to predation will escalate to the point where farming is no longer economically viable. This narrative bases its competing understanding of jackal ecology and management on the “historical experience in the area, on discussions

2 In using the term ‘local knowledge’, instead of ‘indigenous knowledge’ and/or ‘traditional ecological knowledge’, we refer to all non-professional knowledge that is rooted in a particular place (Geertz 1983, cited by Corburn 2003; see also Kloppenburger 1991). This category is less specific than ‘indigenous knowledge’, which refers to the wealth of information that is “unique to a given culture or society” (Agrawal 1995) and ‘traditional ecological knowledge’ which places emphasis on “traditionality” (Green 2008).

with older farmers, and from the insights peddled by professional hunters” (Natrass & Conradie 2015). In an arid and semi-arid environment such as the Karoo, farm-level economics are part of the ‘farmer jackal narrative’ as well. In other words, this narrative is a blend of animal behaviour knowledge and farm economics.

According to Natrass and Conradie (2015), the ‘farmer jackal narrative’, which draws mostly on citizen science and/or applied expertise, is often “brushed aside by environmentalists, who construct farmers as ignorant of ‘the science’ and academic research as the only valid store of knowledge”. This results in conflict between the various parties involved in and/or affected by jackals.

Among farmers, jackals challenge what Philo and Wilbert (2000) have described as the “imaginative geography of animals” by transgressing what the farmers regard as the proper and natural place of jackals in the Karoo. They are adept at bypassing fences, seem to have lost their fear of humans and are able to outsmart various management techniques, which renders controlling them extremely difficult. As with the ambiguous identity of dingoes (*Canis lupus dingo*) in Australia (Hyttén 2009; Van Eeden *et al.* 2020) and coyotes (*Canis latrans*) in North America (Myers 2021), jackals that live and stay in national parks and provincial reserves are constructed differently by farmers and specialist predator hunters. In these purportedly wild or natural areas, jackals are accepted as part of the ecosystem. However, as soon as jackals interfere with the agricultural economy and thwart farmers’ economic interests, they become ‘wanted’ animals that are subverting the ‘natural order’ of things on the farm, a sentiment that was echoed in a study from the Western Cape (Drouilly 2019), and with regard to leopard (*Panthera pardus*) in the Eastern Cape (Minnie 2009). ‘Bernard’, a specialist predator hunter, summed up this distinction succinctly:

*“Jackals have a place in the ecosystem, but remember; this [the farm] is not a natural ecosystem. This is a farming system. Just as you have to reduce your springboks [*Antilope diabolus*] because they eat the pastures. Just as you have to market your lambs because the lambs are too much. Space must be made for it. In the same way, you have to manage the jackals too because they eat your profit.”* (Pers. comm., 19 October 2017)

Farmers are frustrated that life scientists working on jackal ecology and biodiversity management do not seem to take the distinction they are drawing between natural and ‘unnatural’ jackals into consideration. While a few farmers do engage actively with academic material (particularly through informational

communication and social media)—including those scientific papers presenting findings consistent with the strong ‘environmental jackal narrative’ (see, for example, Terblanche 2020)—many accuse ‘academics’ (i.e., ecologists and zoologists) of conducting research exclusively in protected areas and thus ‘getting their science wrong’ (‘Gys’, pers. comm., 15 May 2017; ‘Stefan’, pers. comm., 16 May 2017; ‘Franco’, pers. comm., 18 May 2017). All the farmers and specialist predator hunters interviewed argued strongly that life scientists understate the extent of the predation crisis and the effects thereof, in part because much of their research is not focused on ‘unnatural’ jackals on farmland but on ‘natural’ jackals in protected areas. All of the interviewed farmers unanimously agreed that jackals will consume ‘softer targets’ if they can, i.e., domestic animals such as sheep rather than wild prey; thus, their presence on farms is extremely undesirable and, therefore, ‘unnatural’.

Even though several studies globally, including Africa, have shown that if the population dynamics of predators are disturbed by activities such as hunting, the affected animals may adapt by producing bigger litters, expanding their territories and changing their behaviour (Avenant & du Plessis 2008; Minnie *et al.* 2016), Kareeberg farmers were resistant to the information about these studies that was imparted at the public communication meetings attended between 2016 and 2019. Without more context-specific research in the Kareeberg region, they voiced doubts about the science and dismissed ecologists’ research-based findings as mere hypotheses that their own experiences did not bear out. Even though their own control methods are not working optimally, in as much as farmers continue to face an onslaught from jackal (and caracal), they regard them as more effective than the advice of ecologists to “learn to live with the jackal” which, for them, points to economic disaster.

Farmers’ insecurity in relation to the jackal and the SKA

After the state’s Land Acquisition Programme between 2016 and 2017, the approximately 130,000 ha owned by the NRF were finally declared a national park by South Africa’s Minister of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) in March 2020 (Creecy 2020). Originally in 2019, the Integrated Environmental Management Plan (IEMP) for the site recommended that it be managed as a special nature reserve which would be primarily dedicated to scientific research and environmental monitoring while limiting who may enter the site (President of the Republic of South Africa 2004). Those who are allowed into this type of protected area are predominantly restricted to conservation management, state officials and researchers who are granted exemption (President of

the Republic of South Africa 2004). In other words, visits by the general public and hence commercial eco-tourism are prohibited.

At a closed meeting with neighbouring farmers in 2018, the SARAO’s land acquisition process programme manager stated that while astronomy would remain the SARAO’s primary focus, the SKA core site’s “secondary use is to ensure the protection of the environment/ecosystem through the conservation of biodiversity and the promotion of long-term environmental research and monitoring”. This information was also highlighted at workshops in April 2018, to discuss the development of the SARAO National Park Management Plan in Williston, Brandvlei and Carnarvon, citing that it was part of the SARAO’s “collective responsibility” to support and promote environmental research and conservation.

Natural scientists, especially ecologists, and conservationists have welcomed the positive contribution that they see the SKA core site making towards conservation in the Nama Karoo, adding approximately 41% to the National Protection Areas Expansion Strategy Upper Karoo target (Todd [2017]; see also Hoffman *et al.* 2018). However, only six of the 26 farmers and specialist predator hunters interviewed saw the value of a conservation area, while most views among farmers about the protected area and SANParks’ involvement were extremely negative. Engaging in a co-management agreement with SKA SA, SANParks’ responsibilities include wildlife management, biodiversity conservation, resource management, administrative tasks related to the development and implementation of the management plan, stakeholder engagement, conducting long-term environmental research and monitoring programmes with external parties such as the South African Environmental Observation Network and universities or research institutes, and of particular importance to this research, predator control (SKA SA 2017).

At the workshops held by SANParks and SARAO in April 2018 to discuss the development of the SARAO National Park Management Plan in the small towns of Williston and Carnarvon, the strained relationship between the SARAO and farmers completely dominated proceedings. These tensions were indicative of the miscommunication and lack of trust that had characterised prior interactions with the SKA’s Land Acquisition Programme. Farmers voiced their objections to the fact that “the decisions have already been made” and their mistrust of what was yet another example of the top-down approach of scientists towards farmers. In addition to their concerns that they were not being taken seriously, farmers and specialist predator hunters also cited food security as a concern, with valuable agricultural

land being taken out of production and converted into a protected area.

Towards 30 June 2018, the cut-off date at which farmers who were still leasing their former properties from the SARAO in the SKA core site would have to evacuate their farms, farmers who would be bordering the new park, as well as those further afield, turned their concerns to the impact of this new land use on their farming practices and economics. Predation management emerged as a key issue for farmers, but they came to find that those who were centrally involved with policy development and decision-making regarding jackals continued to dictate not only the terms of jackal management in practice, but also the public discussions related to jackals.

The arrival of the SKA in this farming community in the Karoo has not only brought the struggle regarding appropriate and successful jackal management strategies to the fore, but also the struggle over land and power. This is accompanied by struggles over meaning, nostalgia, belonging, autonomy and authority. Therefore, a very large proportion of farmers in the region surrounding the SKA core site find the presence of the astronomy installation to be deeply disruptive, as it is shifting local power dynamics away from themselves. In the words of one of the farmers at a public meeting on 17 May 2016, the relationship between the towns surrounding the SKA core site and the SARAO is “like an arranged, forced marriage such as in the East”.

Farmers often reminded the SARAO personnel throughout the series of public meetings between 2016 and 2018 that the original picture that had been “sold” to them when the first two farms were acquired for the SKA in 2008, was one of their livestock grazing among the radio telescopes, depicting a happy co-existence between local livelihoods and astronomical science (Terblanche 2020). This point was made again at the workshop with SANParks and SARAO in Williston in April 2018, with one farmer demanding clarity on why springbok and other game species would be allowed to graze among the radio telescopes but not livestock. From their side, the SARAO personnel present justified the decision to clearly mark off the spaces allocated to radio astronomy from those for livestock farming, citing safety and security regulations as well as the low-intensity management strategies required for game. Farmers, however, were not mollified. For them, the primary consideration was that ‘science’ (by which they were referring to both radio astronomy and ecology) was taking precedence over farming. While turning the core site into a protected area would allow the SARAO to contribute to the advancement of science and showcase the achievements of radio astronomy in and for South Africa and Africa, local needs were being disregarded.

The power relations around knowledge production in jackal management

At the time the present study was being conducted, a ‘messy’ management space was emerging around the SKA’s core site, as environmentalists, ecologists and zoologists tried to implement a pro-science management strategy in an area where farmers had adopted a largely hostile approach to the new landowners and management authorities. This fed into an ‘anti-science’ narrative among the new managers, in which farmers were depicted as ignorant and misguided in their disparaging of the objective, rational and bureaucratic approach to the management of the park more generally and jackals specifically; an objective that was embedded in and supported by scientific principles.

The IEMP for the park contains a commitment to long-term environmental research and monitoring, including plans for research on the presence and abundance of mesocarnivores and their prey within the core area (Gaea Enviro (Pty) Ltd 2018). Such evidence, it is argued, will allow SANParks, the land manager of the core site, to make informed decisions about wildlife, including whether jackals in the new protected area should be actively managed or not (Gaea Enviro (Pty) Ltd 2018). According to the SARAO’s stakeholder engagement officer in 2019, studies were being conducted by University of Cape Town postgraduate students in and around the SKA core site which would “determine the movement and the change in numbers” of the jackal (and caracal) populations (pers. comm., 17 July 2019). This information would in turn be linked to a management plan, which SANParks will be responsible for implementing (see SANParks 2022).

The SARAO’s commitment to scientific knowledge in its management of this new and contested protected area was made clear at a closed meeting in May 2018, involving the SARAO personnel and farmers neighbouring the SKA core site. During the discussion, the programme manager for the SARAO’s land acquisition process stated that even though they were well aware of farmers’ concerns regarding problem animals, the SARAO had to follow strict procedures in developing its policies, because the SARAO forms part of an international consortium. In other words, every management decision that is taken by the SARAO needs to be supported by scientific evidence that was not only nationally but internationally acceptable:

“The SKA’s official position is that we [SARAO] do not hunt jackal. [...] We do not have the scientific knowledge yet [i.e. that active hunting solves livestock predation]. But I will go back to management and say this is what the farmers say [that lethal methods should be used] [...] But we must justify our actions. Not only nationally but also internationally.

Farmers’ opinions are not good enough, there must be scientific backing.”

At the same time, the programme manager was also at pains to convey a conciliatory tone to the farmers. While emphasising throughout the meeting that the SARAO had never ruled out shooting jackals and acknowledging the challenges that farmers face in dealing with mesopredators, the programme manager noted that lethal control would only be pursued if scientific evidence supported it. The farmers attending the meeting were, however, not impressed. Because the national park would not be open to tourists, and SANParks would not be responsible for the costs of running the park (in contrast with other national parks), the SARAO’s land acquisition programme manager also described the process as “business unusual”, emphasising the uniqueness of the management mandate for the new park, the region’s ecology, and the global radio astronomy project. Turning her statement against her, ‘Gys’ retorted that since the park is “business unusual”, “no [standard] science and/or livestock practice is feasible”. Picking up the conversation, ‘Franco’ was also dismissive of the need for research. According to him, “the people that do research, do not farm with sheep” and as a result, had no business in saying how farmers should run their farm, including how they should manage their predators.

The above vignette reflects the SKA management’s commitment to an understanding of science as “objective knowledge free from emotions, private interests, bias or prejudice” (Gieryn 1983). Most natural scientists regard these characteristics as constituting the foundation of western science. Some also see their scientific expertise as superior to the knowledge of lay citizens, since the former is based on systematic empirical observation and verification, whereas the latter is based on emotions and values (Gustafsson 2011; Peacock *et al.* 2020). The response from ‘Gys’ quoted above reflects the concerns of numerous farmers who argue that by the time the research projects on mesocarnivores and their impact have been concluded, it will be too late to initiate a management plan for the park as they will already have suffered considerable financial losses because of unchecked jackal predation. These concerns have also been reported in mass media outputs (Jansen 2020; Harrison 2023; Kok 2023).

Given the academics’ (i.e. ecologists and zoologists) lack of experience on the ground (both in terms of livestock farming and in that particular region), and the time it takes to produce scientifically acceptable research results (‘Simoné’, pers. comm., 18 May 2017; ‘Frederick’, pers. comm., 18 May 2017; de Waal 2018, unpubl. data), farmers are forced to rely on their own knowledge and that of their

peers for advice and support (Avenant & du Plessis 2008). According to small mammal ecologist Nico Avenant (pers. comm., 19 February 2018), another reason why farmers revert to their own knowledge regarding jackals and human–jackal conflict and “uses the method which he learnt from his father or [...] from older farmers”, is isolation. In other words, the farmer feels as if “there is no one he can ask advice”. At the same time, there are also strong views on the legitimacy of the experience-based knowledge of the jackal that is to be found on commercial farms.

Rather than farmers learning to “live with the jackal”, respondents felt strongly that the SKA management and its scientific experts needed to learn how to accommodate farmers and their knowledge into their plans for the SKA national park. In the words of one farmer respondent’s wife, “the Karoo does not only have knowledge about the stars”. This local knowledge ranges from practical experience and deep knowledge of the veld to farmer ‘lay experts’ who follow the scientific debates and blend that with their local farm knowledge.

While all interviewed farmers employ fewer permanent farmworkers than they did previously, many still rely on ‘foot soldiers’ to identify and follow spoor and set traps for jackal and caracal as part of their daily routine. In the Kareeberg, these workers are all ‘coloured’³ men, generally middle-aged, with little formal education and living with their families on the farm (Terblanche 2020). In some instances, where farmers have particularly high predation rates, a farmworker may be employed solely for his skills as a foot soldier. As these workers interact with jackals on almost a daily basis, farmers and specialist predator hunters applaud them for their practical knowledge on jackal behaviour they have gained from being in the veld. The majority of interviewed farmers (15 out of 19) admitted that they “cannot go on without them”. Recalling an experience in the veld when his foot soldier operated on a trapped caracal to retrieve the urine to use as a deterrent for other caracals, ‘Gys’ was impressed both by the knowledge this man displayed and by how gently he worked with the animals:

“He puts a choker around [...] his neck. Then he pulls him up, then he hits him lightly over the head with his knob-stick. [...] Then he operates on him. Then he takes out his bladder to catch that urine [...], he operates him and everything. The cat lies there

[...] and then he kills him. Now you can ask why does he do that? [...] When a thing dies, he pees. And then his bladder is empty, then his urine is lost. This that man tells me. [...] He does not have a BSc degree. He doesn’t, and he operates [...] that cat, not a kitten, without him knowing [laughing]!” (Pers. comm., 15 May 2017)

The knowledge that foot soldiers (and hands-on farmers) bring to jackal management in the context of sheep farming in the Karoo is based on deep experience accumulated over many years. In the words of ‘Karel’, a foot soldier, “I walk 20 kilometres a day, Madam. At night I lie awake and listen to the sounds and during the day I rely on my gut feeling and look for spoor, dung and pee”. He knows exactly when it is lambing time, when it is the jackals’ breeding season, where the dens of the jackals are and how to set a foothold trap in such a way that the jackal does not smell him and/or see his footprints. As he described, “you have to think like a jackal, you have to become one”.

The interaction with ‘Karel’ confirmed farmers’ accounts of the personal characteristics of foot soldiers. According to ‘Hugo’, it required a “unique person [and] nature to do the job” (pers. comm., 27 October 2017). ‘Maghiel’ noted that “if you do not love the veld” and do not have an absolute interest in the veld, you will not be able to do this work (pers. comm., 4 July 2017). Farmers were also concerned about the changing social environment and its impact on labour relationships on farms. ‘Maghiel’ for instance, expressed concern that most Karoo foot soldiers were elderly, and this form of local knowledge was dying out; it was not being transmitted to the younger generation (i.e., farmworkers’ children), who were choosing to move away from farm work in general (pers. comm., 4 July 2017). Reasons given for this included labour issues, and the meagre salary among them. In the case of foot soldiers, the long days and nights in the veld, the strenuousness and isolated nature of the work, and most importantly, the inconsistency of the work were identified as particular deterrents.

In addition to foot soldiers, participating farmers also consider other actors, both fellow farmers and specialist predator hunters, to be not simply knowledgeable about, but experts in jackal management. The prime example of a jackal expert is Niel Viljoen, a farmer who has made it central to his farming practice to study the diet and behaviour of jackals. Viljoen has

3 Deriving from the old apartheid classificatory system, the term ‘coloured’ is used as a socio-politically invented racial construct for people of mixed-race descent (Christopher 2002; Devereux 2020). The term continues to shape social identities today (see, for example, Terblanche 2020).

been in a “battle with jackals” since 1990 when he first started farming (pers. comm., 20 May 2017). Over the years, fighting against the jackals evolved into a “passion to understand jackals” for this farmer, avid hunter, and predation management consultant for the NWGA.

As he shifted from reactive (predator) to proactive (predation) management—which involves maintaining and managing his boundary fences, understanding the biology of the jackal and farming around this, as well as actively managing his lambing seasons—and began to achieve success on his farm, his reputation spread like wildfire among other farmers, even reaching into the community of life scientists working on jackal management in the Karoo. Viljoen’s constant message to fellow farmers goes against the grain of much local knowledge and overlaps with those on the ‘science’ side of the divide in the knowledge systems: this is that one cannot ignore jackals and farmers need to accept the reality of jackals on their farms. As a result, the only way to farm successfully is to farm alongside the jackal: “*You must know your property, you must know the jackal’s biology, you must know its behavioural patterns. [...] You are farming with a jackal whether you want to know it or not. He is on your farm*” (N. Viljoen, pers. comm., 20 May 2017).

When asked why farmers view him as “one of the jackal experts” (‘Gys’, pers. comm., 15 May 2017), Viljoen said it was because he and other farmers “speak the same language” (pers. comm., 20 May 2017). Being a farmer himself, Viljoen understands farmers’ concerns and the economic pressures commercial farmers face. However, what differentiates Viljoen from most other Kareeberg farmers is that, in addition to his local knowledge, he also draws on and engages with the ‘environmental jackal narrative’ by being involved in scientific research as well as policymaking (see, for example, Viljoen 2014a, 2014b, 2014c, 2017a, 2017b, 2024). Consequently, all the ecologists and zoologists interviewed in this study had high praise for his ability to bridge social networks.

Adaptive co-management and the way forward

Rutina *et al.* (2017) demonstrated the importance of involving local communities in human–wildlife conflict management by highlighting that local knowledge and skills can be of high quality and help relieve the burden of evidence-based management on state entities at a relatively low cost. McCall and Dunn (2012) and Constant *et al.* (2015) also stressed the importance of incorporating local knowledge and experience in mitigating human–wildlife conflicts. In South Africa, a recent shift towards trans- and multidisciplinary studies has contributed to a better understanding of prevailing situations in specific

areas (Thorn *et al.* 2012, 2013; Constant *et al.* 2015). However, a criticism of local knowledge, even in the form of opinion surveys, is that it is subject to various biases (Kruger 2019). Where data on predation losses and predator control are exaggerated or underreported due to farmers not adequately examining carcasses, lacking the skill and experience to correctly identify causes of livestock losses or other social factors (Lawson 1989; Bekker 1994; Turpie & Akinyemi 2018), the result is inaccurate data or data being unavailable to the scientific community. In addition to the lack of a way for farmers to accurately and reliably report such data, until recently, this may have contributed to scientists and authorities brushing off the inputs of farmers in decision-making processes.

Nevertheless, examining farmers’ perceptions of the problem may assist in devising appropriate management strategies by appreciating the problem from the farmers’ perspective (Lawson 1989). Janse van Rensburg (1991) and Bekker (1994) found some farmers to suffer from psychological stress and frustration, with high levels of suspicion, feeling that they are confronted with a wall of legislation, regulations and permit systems, which also differ between provinces.

A criticism among farmers and hunters of the “holistic” approach to predation management, is that it is outdated information and “guesswork” (de Waal 2023) and that assumptions from some scientific publications are extrapolated to other areas, where they may not be relevant (Bekker 1994; Terblanche 2020). Farmers also do not deem the “theoretical narratives” of researchers with little or no practical experience useful (Bekker 1994). While some contend that research will not address the issues or may not be worthwhile, others have called for research to substantiate or refute “scientific perceptions and views” (de Waal 2023).

The issue of farmers perceiving protected areas to be breeding grounds for potential damage-causing animals also dominated discussions during the 1990s (de Waal 2023). While farmers claimed that conservation authorities were responsible for livestock losses due to predators breeding on and dispersing from state land (Bekker 1994), conservation authorities referred to studies finding no evidence of increased livestock losses on farms bordering protected areas, and that “good conservation management does not serve as a breeding ground for damage-causing animals” (de Waal 2023).

In the South African context, some of the earliest research on human–predator conflict may be regarded as containing an element of local knowledge. The divergence between the two types of knowledge systems likely came about during the 1980s and 1990s,

when work such as that of van der Merwe (1953), which had been based on opinion surveys, was dismissed as not being of a scientific nature (Ferguson 1980), and government assistance in predator management in the agricultural sector was withdrawn (Carruthers & Natrass 2018; Kruger *et al.* 2021; de Waal 2023). Government assistance included research on the ecology and management of damage-causing animals, with the goal to develop more effective and ecologically more responsible management strategies (Kruger 2019; de Waal 2023). The research was conducted by nature conservation officials tasked with problem animal control, under the premise that to ensure the most effective management of damage-causing animals, management should be based on scientific methods (Hey 1964).

Natrass and Conradie (2015) and Natrass *et al.* (2020b) do note that some of the scientific claims of jackal ecologists support elements of the ‘farmer jackal narrative’, for example, that litter size increases with greater food supply and that jackals’ sense of territoriality is more relaxed when resources are abundant. Thus, it is clear that ‘scientific’ and ‘local’ knowledge systems are not always competing with each other, and farmers may incorporate scientific data into their local knowledge if the former is consistent with their farm-based experience. This is not dissimilar to the way in which the proponents of the ‘environmental jackal narrative’ tend to favour new scientific work that confirms their already established understanding (see, for example, Ashton-James & Tracy 2012).

At the study site, the distinction between the two narratives is not absolute, and conversations and some cross-fertilisation can occur among the advocates of each. Therefore, the discourses surrounding nature, the environment and, we would add, animals, “cannot be seen as simple rhetoric or ideology, but rather as more deeply contested truths, that people form and defend based on highly variable personal, idiosyncratic, experiences” (Robbins 2004, cited by Bidwell 2009).

Recently, research focusing on the human–jackal conflict on farms has increased (e.g., Jansen 2016 in Namaqualand; Natrass & Conradie 2015; Conradie & Natrass 2017; Drouilly *et al.* 2017, 2018, 2020, 2021; Viljoen 2017c; Natrass & Conradie 2018; Natrass *et al.* 2020a in the Central Karoo; and Whitehouse-Tedd *et al.* 2021 in the Kalahari). However, apart from Blanckenberg (2021), a shortage of up-to-date, context-specific research on jackals and the human–jackal conflict in the Nama Karoo remains (de Waal, unpubl. data, 2018; N. Natrass, pers. comm., 17 January 2018; N. Avenant, pers. comm., 19 February 2018).

A crucial aspect of strategies to mitigate human–wildlife conflicts is multidisciplinary and full participation of the main stakeholders since the management of human–wildlife conflicts is a human management issue (Muruthi 2005; du Plessis 2013; Terblanche 2015, 2020). Furthermore, farmers’ choice of method to manage predation is also driven not only by efficacy, practical and economic considerations but also by social factors (e.g. cultural and ethical considerations, lifestyle choices and social cohesion) (Bekker 1994; Turpie & Akinyemi 2018; Terblanche 2020). Therefore, a greater focus on the dynamics of the social factors that shape the conflicts is indispensable for making meaningful advances in human–wildlife conflict in southern Africa.

Technologies currently available (Kruger 2019; Luyt 2020; Kruger *et al.* 2021) have the potential to incorporate local expertise in a scientific manner in situations such as those described in this paper. The consensus among prominent role-players in predation management is that management should be adaptive (du Plessis *et al.* 2018). The concept of adaptive management agrees with Kloppenburg’s (1991) and Knapp and Fernandez-Gimenez’s (2009) descriptions of how local knowledge is produced, corroborating the motivation for improving relations between groupings such as, in the case of this study, farmers/hunters and the scientific community. However, a vital aspect of such processes, aside from incorporating the inputs of the farming community, is the continuous evaluation of their perceptions (Constant *et al.* 2015).

CONCLUSION

A large body of work emphasises the importance of pluralist decision-making perspectives in wildlife management as “foundational to transactional management”, because it “accounts for the multiple views of reality among stakeholders” (Zollinger & Daniels 2005). The establishment of the Meerkat National Park is, however, being managed rather differently. Here, formal processes of consultation are in place, as required by national legislation, but ultimately it is the scientific knowledge of external decision-makers and physicists attached to the SKA and academic ecologists and zoologists working on jackals that is dominant regarding proposed wildlife management on the SKA core site. Consistent with the theoretical insights of political ecology, this research has shown that in the decision-making related to jackal management and the future usage of the SKA core site, the management decisions that are made are embedded in relations of power and authority. In defending management decisions that have often already been made, both managers and scientists use the language of science to silence and disempower those challenging their authority.

The professional elites who are centrally involved with policy development and decision-making regarding jackals continue to dictate not only the terms of jackal management in practice, but also define the scope of the public discussions related to jackals, based on their perceived scientific expertise as well as their occupation of key positions in the institutions tasked with responsibility for environmental management at the new park. In this way they also impact on the lives of the farmers living around the SKA core site, who fall outside the land over which they have direct control. Although the SRAO has organised numerous public meetings in the towns surrounding the core site since South Africa won the bid to co-host the SKA in 2012, the farmers neighbouring and in the vicinity of the SKA core site have not been identified as a special interest group.⁴ Rather, they have had to voice their concerns as members of the broader ‘local community’ that is invited to attend these meetings as local stakeholders. Arguably, the equally pressing, but very different, concerns raised by residents of the neighbouring small towns, which centre on job creation, economic development and social upliftment (Butler 2018; Walker & Chinigò 2018; Gastrow & Oppelt 2019), have overshadowed those of the small group of farmers now bordering the SKA core site. Given the continued significance of sheep farming for the local economy including in the future when more black farmers can be expected to be involved, views and experiences of farmers and their workers are important.

Manfredo (2008) has argued persuasively that in order to move away from human–human conflict in wildlife management, with opposing groups focused on discrediting the position of their opponents, wildlife managers, along with other interest groups involved, should focus on areas of agreement, to facilitate social engagement (see also Sidaway 2005). An essential aspect of facilitating engagement is for those in positions of power to utilise an

interdisciplinary approach and engage seriously with local knowledge and what it can bring to the analysis of jackal behaviour in particular and more sustainable farming practices in general. What is needed to counter the top-down approach that has been evident in the style of jackal management around the SKA core site and new national park, are experts able to transcend the ‘environmental’ and ‘farmer jackal narratives’, and to draw together the available scientific and local expertise as resources. Incorporating local knowledge in the development of policy and design of the structures needed to implement them will promote a wider acceptance of the SKA project and Meerkat National Park within the Kareeberg area. It will decrease the farming community’s sense of marginalisation and contribute to building trust among the different interest groups concerned about the future of the significant new developments in their area. In terms of the human–wildlife conflict it will certainly enhance the prospects for more effective and sustainable jackal management in the specific context of the SKA core site.

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⁴ Although more research is required on this, this is consistent with the marginalised status of commercial farmers as a constituency within broader debates on land and agrarian reform in South Africa (Walker & Chinigò 2018; Chinigò 2019; Walker 2019; Terblanche 2020).

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